

Antimicrobial Agents—Part IV⁺ : Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Some New Arylsulfonylhydrazones Derived from 5-Substituted-2-Furaldehydes and 3-(5-Nitro-2-Furyl) Acrolein[†]

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Several new arylsulfonylhydrazones derived from variously 5-substituted-2-furaldehydes and 3-(5-nitro-2-furyl) acrolein have been synthesized and screened *in vitro* for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

ARYLSULFONYLHYDRAZONES of 2-furaldehyde and 5-nitro-2-furaldehyde have been reported to possess antibacterial activity¹ and are also useful as anticoccidial agents² in poultry. A recent communication by Juneau *et al*³ on some arylsulfonylhydrazones derived from various heterocycles has prompted us to report our work on the synthesis and antimicrobial screening of a number of new related hydrazones of 5-substituted-2-furaldehydes and 3-(5-nitro-2-furyl) acrolein, prepared as a part of our continued search for biologically active furan derivatives⁴⁻⁶, corresponding to structure I.

The various arylsulfonyl hydrazides required as starting materials were prepared by reacting the respective sulfonyl chlorides with 80% NH₂NH₂·H₂O in THF following the standard procedures⁷. However *p*-aminobenzenesulfonyl hydrazide was obtained from its sulfonyl fluoride⁸ according to

the method of Jensen⁹. Although 5-butylthio-2-furaldehyde was reported in literature¹⁰, its physical characteristics were not described. It has now been prepared by us by the condensation of 5-bromo-2-furaldehyde with butanethiol in boiling toluene in the presence of sodium methoxide and

was characterized through its semicarbazone. 5-(*p*-Nitrophenyl)-2-furaldehyde¹¹ and 3-(5-nitro-2-furyl) acrolein¹² were made according to known methods, while 5-(*p*-nitrophenoxy)- and 5-(*p*-chlorophenoxy)-2-furaldehydes were prepared as described earlier¹³.

The desired arylsulfonylhydrazones(I) were synthesized in excellent yields (Table 1) by reacting the respective sulfonyl hydrazides with appropriate aldehyde and were isolated as bright yellow crystalline solids. These compounds were characterized by their mode of synthesis and elemental analyses. Their structures were further confirmed by IR spectra, which showed the characteristic absorption bands around 3,180-3,200 (NH) and 1360-1380 and 1160-1180 cm⁻¹ (-SO₂-).

All the compounds reported in Table 1 were screened *in vitro* for their antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in closed glass capillary tubes using sulfuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in nujol on a Perkin-Elmer 237 grating spectrophotometer. Elemental analyses were performed using Höpli Microcombustion apparatus MK 101.

5-Butylthio-2-Furaldehyde :

Sodium methoxide (5.4 g, 0.1 mol) in absolute methanol (40 ml) and butanethiol (9.0 g, 0.1 mol) were added simultaneously dropwise into dry toluene (80 ml) and the mixture was heated at 60-80° for 15 minutes. To this was added dropwise a solution of 5-bromo-2-furaldehyde (17.5 g,

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TABLE 1—ARYLSULFONYLHYDRAZONES(I*)

Comp. No.	Z	Y	R	m.p. °C	Yield %	Solvent of Crystallisation
1.	SC ₄ H ₉	—	CH ₃	82-84	82	MeOH
2.	SC ₄ H ₉	—	Cl	124-26	81	MeOH
3.	SC ₄ H ₉	—	NH ₂	94-96	78	EtOAc-Pet. ether
4.	SC ₄ H ₉	—	NHCOCH ₃	190-92	90	MeOH
5.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	CH ₃	204-06d	82	AcOH
6.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	Cl	205-07d	79	AcOH
7.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	NH ₂	210d	76	EtOAc-Pet. ether
8.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	—	NHCOCH ₃	206-28d	82	AcOH
9.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -O-	—	CH ₃	172-73	87	AcOH
10.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -O-	—	Cl	182-83	82	AcOH
11.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -O-	—	NH ₂	170-71	70	EtOAc-Pet. ether
12.	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ -O-	—	NHCOCH ₃	192d	92	AcOH
13.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -O-	—	CH ₃	123-25	80	EtOAc-Pet. ether
14.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -O-	—	Cl	144-46	80	EtOAc-Pet. ether
15.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -O-	—	NH ₂	190-92	66	EtOAc
16.	<i>p</i> -ClC ₆ H ₄ -O-	—	NHCOCH ₃	184-86	92	MeOH
17.	NO ₂	CH=CH	CH ₃	132-34	90	MeOH
18.	NO ₂	CH=CH	Cl	158-60	79	MeOH
19.	NO ₂	CH=CH	NH ₂	142-44	72	MeOH
20.	NO ₂	CH=CH	NHCOCH ₃	206-08d	86	MeOH

* Satisfactory analysis for C, H and N were obtained.
d Decomposition.

0.1 mol) in dry toluene (40 ml) during 0.5 hr with stirring. The reaction mixture was heated under reflux at 120-130° for 4 hr in an oil bath. The contents were then cooled to 50°, filtered to remove NaBr and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The residue was distilled under vacuum to yield 11 g (59%) of the title compound as colourless liquid, b.p. 126-128° (10 mm); Semicarbazone; m.p. 128-130° (MeOH) (Found: C, 49.44; H, 5.97; N, 17.66. C₁₀H₁₅N₃O₂S requires C, 49.79; H, 6.22; N, 17.43%).

Arylsulfonylhydrazones (I, Table 1) :

General procedure :

A mixture of arylsulfonylhydrazide (0.01 mol) and appropriate aldehyde (0.01 mol) in methanol (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 hr. The reaction mixture was concentrated under reduced pressure and cooled in ice. The resulting solids were filtered, washed with methanol and recrystallized from suitable solvent (Table 1) to give the pure compounds as bright yellow crystalline solids.

Biological screening results :

All the compounds reported in Table 1 were tested *in vitro* for their antibacterial activity by serial dilution tube method and antifungal activity by agar dilution assay method as described earlier*. The highest dilution of the test compound which inhibited the visual growth of the organism was taken as minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC, µg/ml). The bacteria employed were *S. aureus*,

S. typhi, *E. coli*, *A. tumefaciens*, *B. subtilis* and *M. tuberculosis* H₃₇RV and the fungi used were *C. albicans*, *Cr. neoformans*, *T. mentagrophytes*, *M. canis* and *A. niger*.

Out of all the compounds studied, the arylsulfonylhydrazones derived from 3-(5-nitro-2-furyl) acrolein alone showed moderate antimicrobial activity, while the remaining were completely inactive against all the organisms at the maximum test concentrations (100 µg/ml). Thus compound Nos 17-20 were found to be active against *S. aureus*, *S. typhi*, *E. coli* and *A. tumefaciens* at 12.5-25.0 µg/ml. These four compounds also exhibited moderate antifungal activity against *T. mentagrophytes*, *M. canis* and *A. niger* at 12.5-25.0 µg/ml but were inactive against *C. albicans*. None of these compounds showed any significant antituberculosis activity.

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